

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: ScotRail

Rethinking Mobility: Reducing
Car Miles Through Rail and
Road Insights in Scotland

**27 January 2025 -
7 February 2025**

Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
2	Introduction	5
2.1	Background of the Challenge	5
2.2	Problem Statement	5
3	Data	7
3.1	Dataset description	7
3.2	Case study event descriptions	8
3.2.1	Edinburgh Fringe Festival	8
3.2.2	Ayr station fire	9
3.3	Data quality	9
4	Approach	11
4.1	Understanding Disruptions On ScotRail Network	11
4.1.1	Building the ScotRail network	11
4.1.2	Network data	11
4.1.3	Analysis of ScotRail Network data	13
4.1.4	Unplanned Changes to Services	14
4.2	Estimating Carbon Emissions	21
4.3	Exploratory Data Analysis	24
4.3.1	EDA of Road Traffic Data	24
5	Results & Discussions	30
5.1	ScotRail: Network Disruptions Insights	30
5.1.1	Key metrics to measure disruptions	30
5.1.2	Evaluating Disruption Impact - Ayr Station Fire Incident . . .	32
5.1.3	Interactive demo of ScotRail Network	34
6	Conclusions and Future Work	35
7	Team members	38
	References	40

This work was part funded by the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (DESNZ) through the AI for Decarbonisation Virtual Centre of Excellence (ADViCE) within the AI for Decarbonisation Innovation Programme and part funded by the Data-Centric Engineering Programme via the Lloyd's Register Foundation.

1 Executive Summary

The Scottish Government aims for Net-Zero emissions by 2045, with transport accounting for 36% of Scotland's GHG emissions. Private vehicle use is a major contributor, particularly for commuting and long-distance travel.

This project, a collaboration between ScotRail and The Alan Turing Institute, investigates how rail and road data can support sustainable mobility, reduce car miles, and enhance rail network resilience. The study explores the impact of rail disruptions on travel behaviour, models network-wide effects, and estimates carbon emissions.

The study analyses May 2023–July 2024 ScotRail datasets, including rail usage, passenger counts, road traffic, and external events. Two key case studies illustrate disruption impacts: the Edinburgh Fringe Festival (Aug 2023), which increased rail demand, and the Ayr Station Fire (Sep 2023), which caused a modal shift to road transport.

We apply network science, statistical analysis, and emissions modelling to assess disruption effects. Metrics such as passenger fluctuations, delay patterns, and road traffic changes help quantify impacts. Carbon emissions are estimated using UK government factors.

Rail disruptions lead to increased car usage, as seen in the Ayr Station fire, where road traffic rose significantly. Even after rail services resumed, passenger numbers remained lower, indicating potential long-term behavioural shifts.

Passenger count is a better disruption metric than delays, as seen during the Edinburgh Fringe and storm warnings. While delays remained stable, passenger numbers fluctuated significantly, demonstrating sensitivity to external factors.

Rail can significantly reduce car miles, particularly during high-demand events. Analysis shows that shifting 1,000 passengers from cars to trains can cut emissions by 2,400 kg CO₂e per trip. Targeted incentives and improved service planning could enhance this shift.

Key rail hubs are critical for network stability. Disruptions at Glasgow Queen Street or Edinburgh Waverley can have widespread effects. The Edinburgh–Glasgow corridor is the busiest, underscoring the need for resilience planning.

To improve rail resilience, predictive disruption models and enhanced contingency

planning should be developed. Encouraging a modal shift to rail requires targeted pricing incentives, real-time traffic data, and better last-mile connectivity.

More accurate disruption forecasting can be achieved by integrating real-time road and rail data, incorporating weather and event schedules into planning. Expanding carbon emissions modelling through a real-time emissions dashboard and evaluating service frequency strategies can support sustainability goals.

This study underscores the interconnected nature of Scotland's transport network and the need to minimise rail disruptions to prevent increased reliance on cars. By leveraging data-driven approaches, policymakers and ScotRail can take steps toward a more sustainable, resilient rail system, supporting Scotland's Net-Zero 2045 target.

2 Introduction

2.1 Background of the Challenge

The Government of Scotland has set an ambitious target to achieve Net-Zero by 2045, contributing to the broader UK target of 2050. In this pursuit, the transportation sector plays a critical role, accounting for approximately 36% of the country's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Despite its significance, progress in reducing transport-related emissions has been notably sluggish. A longitudinal study spanning from 1990 to 2023 reveals that while most sectors have seen significant declines in GHG emissions, domestic transport emissions have lagged [3] (see Figure 1) . For example, between 1990 and 2019, emissions from domestic transport fell by only 12%, in stark contrast to more substantial reductions in other sectors. This disparity underscores that domestic transport remains a major contributor to the UK's overall emissions, highlighting the urgent need for targeted measures to reduce its environmental impact.

Scotland's transport landscape further accentuates the challenge. According to Scotland's Transport Census report [1], 62.4% of Scotland's employed population relies on cars for their daily commute, whereas only 3.7% use trains. Given that a significant portion of car miles driven, especially on longer journeys, could feasibly be substituted by rail travel, there is a compelling need to explore and promote alternative modes of transport.

ScotRail, a publicly owned company that operates the majority of Scotland's passenger rail services, is central to these efforts. This report is developed within the context of the Data Study Group project at The Alan Turing Institute in collaboration with ScotRail.

2.2 Problem Statement

The problem is defined as replacing more car miles with railway usage. The main challenges lie in four key areas:

- A key challenge in this work is the lack of integrated, cross-sector data. While recent improvements have provided detailed insights into rail ticket usage, there is still a significant gap in data that combines both road and rail information. This missing link makes it difficult to understand how

Figure 1: Proportion of territorial emissions from domestic transport 1990-2023. In 1990, transport was the third highest emitting sector at 16%, but rose to 29% in 2023.

specific disruption events, such as those defined by their duration and severity impact overall transportation usage.

- We currently lack a clear understanding of how rail disruptions affect road traffic and, consequently, how these shifts influence carbon emissions.
- There are also no proven methodologies available to reliably correlate rail and road traffic data to predict future travel patterns during disruptions.
- Without robust decarbonization scenario models, it is challenging to assess the impact of local events on emissions.

Addressing these issues is critical for developing effective strategies to manage transportation networks and reduce environmental impact.

3 Data

3.1 Dataset description

ScotRail provided participants with access to datasets based on rail and road transport activity over May 2023 to July 2024. The dataset consists of multiple tables capturing operational performance, passenger behaviour, and external influences. Each entry in a dataset corresponds to travel patterns across different train service lines or segments. Additionally, external factors such as weather and events contribute to the analysis of travel behaviour. The sensors collected data continuously by recording cumulative counts (e.g., number of passengers/cars over time). Missing data is retained in the dataset and is clearly marked (e.g., as NaN). No aggregations or imputations were applied to the raw data. An overview of the various datasets is provided below.

Rail Usage Data

This dataset includes:

- Train routes with origin, stops, and destination details.
- Station names associated with each service.
- Rail capacity, including available seats and total capacity.
- Planned and actual train departure and arrival times.
- Disruption and cancellation records, including delay reasons.

Rail Passenger Count Data

Passenger volumes are captured using two independent methodologies:

- Ticket Scans: Data collected from ticket validation points at train stations in Scotland to track boarding and alighting patterns.
- Automatic Passenger Counting (APC) Sensors: Data from doorway-mounted sensors on trains, providing real-time passenger occupancy levels.

Road Traffic Data

This dataset captures vehicular movement and congestion patterns. It includes:

- Geographic positioning and traffic flow direction.
- Classification of vehicle types (e.g., private cars, motorcycles, HGVs).
- Traffic volume data segmented by time and location.

External Events Dataset

This dataset records major external factors influencing transport patterns, such as:

- Public events (e.g., concerts, football matches, large gatherings).
- Weather conditions affecting road and rail transport reliability.
- Road maintenance and accident reports impacting traffic flow and commuter behaviour.

3.2 Case study event descriptions

This report examines the impact of two contrasting real-world events on Scotland's transport network: the Edinburgh Fringe Festival and the Ayr station fire. These case studies were selected due to their distinct nature—one being a planned, large-scale cultural event attracting millions of visitors, and the other an unplanned infrastructure disruption with immediate consequences. By analysing both events, we aim to assess how different types of disturbances—predictable versus unexpected—affect mobility patterns, infrastructure capacity, and modal shifts between rail and road networks. The following subsections provide background on each event and outline the temporal and spatial scope of the analysis.

3.2.1 Edinburgh Fringe Festival

The Edinburgh Fringe Festival (EFF) is one of the world's largest arts and comedy festivals, attracting around 3 million visitors over the course of a single month. This influx of people has a profound impact on the city's transport system. Many

visitors rely on cars to travel from other parts of Scotland and the UK, increasing car dependency. As a result, the city experiences severe congestion, and the rise in road traffic contributes to a significant increase in CO₂ emissions. For this report, we focus on the 2023 EFF event. The event took place from 3 to 28 August.

3.2.2 Ayr station fire

On September 25, 2023, the Ayr station on the Ayrshire Coast Line running to and from Glasgow Central experienced a complete shutdown due to a fire outage at a nearby hotel (Fig. 2 A). All train lines through the station were suspended. Ayr station was closed and was not operational for the remainder of the period studied. The nearby stations to Ayr City were also not operational for a few days in the accident's immediate aftermath, namely the Newton-on-Ayr, Prestwick Town, and Prestwick International Airport. This study aims to analyse the disruption of such an event on the rail and road network, both in the immediate vicinity and far along the transport routes.

Figure 2: Ayr station fire A. Illustration of Ayr hotel fire, B. Map of ScotRail stations closer to Ayr stations. Red rectangle covers the three stations closed for few days in the immediate aftermath

3.3 Data quality

In terms of data quality, following aspects were considered inspired by [5]:

- Appropriateness: The data were relevant to understanding the behaviour of rail and road users, providing insight into transport choices and potential

mode changes.

- **Readiness:** The data was well-documented, with detailed metadata provided for each dataset component, including station information, transport routes, and capacity details.
- **Reliability / Bias:** Passenger counts from ticket scans and APC sensors may have discrepancies due to incomplete data reporting. Also, road traffic data may be affected by inaccuracies in vehicle classification and timestamp precision. In addition to this, external event data relies on public sources and may not capture all relevant disruptions.
- **Sensitivity:** ScotRail deemed the provided data sensitive and therefore had to be analysed in a trusted virtual environment.
- **Sufficiency:** Some datasets exhibit missing or incomplete entries, particularly in passenger counting and event impact tracking. The sample size is sufficient for broad trend analysis but may require augmentation for deeper inferential modelling.

4 Approach

4.1 Understanding Disruptions On ScotRail Network

To assess how disruptions affect passenger mobility and connectivity across Scotland's rail infrastructure, network analysis was employed as a methodological tool. By modelling the ScotRail system as a graph of stations (nodes) and rail connections (edges), we can quantitatively evaluate the structural impacts of both planned and unplanned events. The objective of this section is to construct the underlying ScotRail network and derive relevant sub-networks to facilitate the analysis of the disruptions caused by the Edinburgh Fringe Festival and the Ayr station fire.

4.1.1 Building the ScotRail network

The rail operational information data set provides the time of operations and a detailed account of the routes (origin, stops, and destination) for each rail service line. This dataset was used to build the full ScotRail network map based on the rail lines that ran on a given day (Fig. 3A shows the network map based on July 15, 2023 rail operational data). Similarly, the Edinburgh to Glasgow network sub-graph (illustrated in Fig. 3B) was derived from the full ScotRail network by filtering all the stations (and respective edges between them) that serve the rail lines that run between.

4.1.2 Network data

The network data added to the nodes and edges of the ScotRail network are based on a 1-day aggregation of respective variables. The following data was added as node and edge attributes.

- Node attributes:
 - *location*: Location data (long, lat). Unit: degrees
 - *avg_delay_time_mins*: Difference in time between the planned and the actual time of all trains that run in that station. Unit: Minutes.
- Edge attributes:
 - *distance_miles*: Distance between connected stations. Unit: Miles

Figure 3: ScotRail network visualization. Nodes represent the rail stations and edges represent the rail routes between adjacent stations A. Full ScotRail Network, B. Network subgraph that serves the Edinburgh to Glasgow rail route

- *avg_planned_travel_time_mins*: Average planned travel time (time-tabled) between connected stations. Unit: Minutes.
- *avg_actual_travel_time_mins*: Average actual travel time. Unit: Minutes
- *passenger_count_tickettracker*: Average passenger count based on ticket scans. Unit: count
- *avg_tt_occupancy_capacity_ratio*: Average train occupancy ratio based on total passengers counted by ticket scans and total capacity of the given train. Unit: ratio
- *avg_travel_time_delay_mins*: Average travel time delay between connected stations based on the difference between planned travel time and actual travel time. Unit: Minutes
- *avg_speed_milesperhour*: Average speed of the train between connected stations based on actual travel time and distance. Unit: Miles/Hour

	num_trains	distance	planned_travel_time	actual_travel_time	passenger_count	pc_capacity_ratio	travel_delay	travel_speed
num_trains	1.000000	-0.374286	-0.401736	-0.416320	0.034912	-0.133039	-0.093630	-0.298552
distance	-0.374286	1.000000	0.939926	0.925497	0.210869	0.247818	-0.020916	0.632366
planned_travel_time	-0.401736	0.939926	1.000000	0.979372	0.161949	0.257006	-0.048341	0.443618
actual_travel_time	-0.416320	0.925497	0.979372	1.000000	0.141132	0.255388	0.154487	0.396389
passenger_count	0.034912	0.210869	0.161949	0.141132	1.000000	0.837375	-0.094211	0.258648
pc_capacity_ratio	-0.133039	0.247818	0.257006	0.255388	0.837375	1.000000	0.005782	0.159428
travel_delay	-0.093630	-0.020916	-0.048341	0.154487	-0.094211	0.005782	1.000000	-0.209668
travel_speed	-0.298552	0.632366	0.443618	0.396389	0.258648	0.159428	-0.209668	1.000000

Figure 4: Correlation matrix: Relationship between ScotRail network data given by node and edge weights

4.1.3 Analysis of ScotRail Network data

Figure 5 shows the network visualisation with some of the network data such as the average delay time at the stations (node weight) and the number of rail services that ran between the stations (edge weight). The edge between Edinburgh and Haymarket shows the highest number of rail services being run between them, and hence a potentially critical node in the network. Edinburgh Waverley, which serves one of the two biggest cities, Edinburgh, is a peripheral node in the ScotRail network, while Glasgow city with three main stations is well connected to the rest of the ScotRail. Figure 4 shows the correlation matrix between selected network edge weights. The number of rail services is likely to be 40% lower between stations that are farther apart and/or take a long time to travel. All other relationship has a low correlation (<25%), ignoring the correlated relationships like distance and travel time.

Figure 5: ScotRail network visualisation with data. Data aggregated day: 22 May 2024. Nodes are coloured by the average delay time experienced in the station. Edges are coloured by the number of rail services that run through the edges. Red-coloured nodes represent the stations in the shortest route between Edinburgh Waverley and Glasgow Central station. Darker green nodes indicate a higher average delay time.

4.1.4 Unplanned Changes to Services

To analyse train delays and disruptions across different ScotRail lines, we categorised train activity based on station stops and status records. Our goal was to detect instances of delays, partial disruptions (where a train fails to stop at an expected station), and cancellations, and analyse if the general behaviour corresponds to that of important events and traffic analysis.

For the dataset given by ScotRail, the CapacityReport table represents the long-term planned services, detailing scheduled departure and arrival times. Conversely, the Journeys_SoW table records the actual services operated on a given day, allowing us to track deviations from the planned schedule.

Our primary approach involved performing exclusive joins between the CapacityReport and Journeys_SoW tables using CapacityID to detect service changes.

- Left-exclusive join: Used to identify cancellations, as it highlights planned services that were not recorded in the actual operations.
- Right-exclusive join: Helps detect additional or unscheduled services, capturing instances where trains operated despite not being originally scheduled.

While this approach provides a high-level view of service changes, it is important to note that a cancellation does not always imply that the entire service was removed. Some cancellations were partial, meaning the origin or destination station was modified. In such cases, a corresponding additional service (identified through the right-exclusive join) could reflect the adjusted schedule.

A specific delay analysis was conducted using the UA_Segments table given by ScotRail, which provided granular insights into individual train segments and their status at each station.

Cancellations The first key step in identifying disruptions was analysing cancellations through the left-exclusive join, as shown in Figure 6. This method captures all planned services that were not recorded in the actual operations dataset.

Figure 6: Venn diagram where the red highlighted set shows all long-term planned journeys that did not happen

By aggregating cancellation counts over time, we observed that cancellations were significantly higher at the beginning of the year - see Figure 7. This is likely due to bank holidays and first-half-of-the-year celebrations. The number of cancellations steadily decreased until October 2023, where we detected a sharp increase. This increase aligns with the Ayr Station Hotel fire in late September 2023, which heavily impacted ScotRail services in the surrounding areas.

According to ScotRail after around more than two months of replacement bus services, a shuttle train between Ayr and Prestwick was introduced on December 4th allowing passengers to connect to and from Glasgow services.

Figure 7: Number of cancellations

To deepen our understanding of cancellations, we computed cancellations by origin station. This revealed that Ayr had the highest number of missing trains, with disruptions extending to nearby stations, specifically most lines passing through there, with the Origin destination being somewhere nearby.

According to Ayr Advertiser, the fire has also meant ScotRail has been unable to gain access to train maintenance facilities to the south of Ayr station, with a knock-on effect on services elsewhere in Ayrshire and beyond as a result.

As we can see from Figure 8, stations further down and linked with Ayr also suffered from this knock-off effect such as Girvan and Stranraer. However, other stations in the Glasgow-Ayr direct line, like Kilmarnock, suffered from this as well. During this time, it would not be surprising to see an increase in buses (bus-replacement services) contributing to the traffic volume before the temporary train shuttle was introduced.

Additionally, major hubs such as Glasgow and Edinburgh also exhibited high cancellation counts, likely due to their high traffic and interconnectivity with affected lines. Cancellations at Inverness were most likely to affect trains departing from Wick.

Figure 8: Missing trains by origin station.

Additions The first key step in identifying additional or unscheduled services was analysing right-exclusive joins, as shown in Figure 9. This method captures all actual train services that were not originally planned in the long-term schedule.

Figure 9: Venn diagram where red-highlighted set shows additional services not planned

From Figure 10, there is a slight increase from July to August of 2023, most likely due to the Edinburgh Fringe Festival. After October, there is a sharp increase in December 2023. This coincides with the train shuttle between Ayr and Prestwick Town stations, calling at Newton-on-Ayr, introduced in December as stated above, after about two months of bus-replacement services. After December of 2023, we see a slow decrease until June 2024, when the shuttle was withdrawn.

Figure 10: Number of Additions

Delays by Segment Figure 11 illustrates the top 10 train stations with the highest number of delays, categorised into Mild Delay, Severe Delay, and Early. Edinburgh Waverley and Glasgow Queen St. High Level show the highest counts of mild delays, both exceeding 45 incidents. Aberdeen, Dundee, and Haymarket also report substantial mild delays. Severe delays are significantly fewer across all stations, with Aberdeen and Glasgow Queen St. High Level showing slightly higher numbers. Early arrivals are minimal and mostly observed at Perth, Stirling, and Edinburgh Waverley. Overall, mild delays dominate the delay profile at all major stations in the dataset.

Average delays on weekdays Figure 12 highlights the distribution of missing or delayed train journeys across different hours of the day. Delays begin to rise after 6 a.m., peaking around 12 p.m. and again at 3 p.m. and 7 p.m., with each peak reaching close to or above 25 incidents. A noticeable dip occurs between 1 p.m. and 2 p.m., suggesting fewer scheduled services or improved punctuality. After 8 p.m., delays decline sharply and remain low through the late evening hours. This trend indicates that midday and early evening are the most disruption-prone periods, likely reflecting higher service frequency and commuter volume.

Figure 11: Delays by segment stations

Figure 12: Average delays per hour on weekdays

4.2 Estimating Carbon Emissions

The analysis begins with data exploration that focuses on origin-destination (OD) trip analysis and traffic flow patterns. For OD we used ScotRail passenger data between Glasgow Queen Street and Edinburgh Waverley route for the following dates:

- Start date: 1st August 2023
- End date: 31st August 2023
- Number of Trains
- Number of Passengers

For traffic flow, we used traffic flow on the M8 route (motorway) that goes from Glasgow to Edinburgh.

- Start date: 1st August 2023
- End date: 31st August 2023
- Number of Vehicles
- Type of Vehicles

Based on the analysis of the transportation network, another dimension incorporating CO₂ emissions has been added, as the main aim of the project is to reduce car miles through increased railway usage. This objective is quantified by measuring CO₂ emissions. We use emission levels from the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (DESNZ)'s 2024 emission conversion factors, designed for UK and international organisations to report greenhouse gas emissions ([URL here](#)). We specifically utilise the condensed version of the 2024 toolkit, which is suitable for most users.

Our analysis focuses on CO₂e (carbon dioxide equivalent) emissions based on car sizes, with rail emissions assessed per kilometre for comparison.

According to the report, the average CO₂e emissions per car in the UK are 169g/km. However, for newly registered cars in 2023, the average emissions were lower at 109.3g/km² ([link](#)). Notably, emissions vary significantly by vehicle type and fuel source. In 2024, luxury petrol cars recorded the highest emissions among all car types, reaching nearly 200g/km of CO₂e. As a starting point, however, we simplify the vehicle types by small, medium, and large.

Type	Unit	kg CO ₂ e
Small car	km	0.140
	miles	0.225
Medium car	km	0.168
	miles	0.270
Large car	km	0.207
	miles	0.333
Average car	km	0.169
	miles	0.273

Table 1: CO₂e Emissions for Cars by Size and Distance Unit

Type	Unit	kg CO ₂ e
National Rail	passenger km	0.035

Table 2: CO₂e Emissions for rail and Distance Unit

Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions can be calculated using the formula:

$$\text{GHG Emissions} = \text{Activity Data} \times \text{Emission Conversion Factor}$$

Key Terms

- GHG (CO₂e): CO₂e is the exchange rate of other greenhouse gases to carbon.
- Activity Data: Refers to factors such as the distance traveled and the number of people involved.
- Emission Conversion Factor: Derived from DESNZ (see Table 1 and Table 2).

Example Calculations Mid-size car driving 75 km:

- Average car occupancy: 2.5 persons.

- Calculation:

$$\frac{1000}{2.5} \times 75 \times 0.169 \text{ kg} = 5,095 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e}$$

Five railway services travelling 75 km:

- Average number of people per service: 200.
- Calculation:

$$5 \times 200 \times 75 \times 0.035 \text{ kg} = 2,659 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e}$$

This example of CO₂e emission calculation, which integrates a holistic analysis of railway and road traffic volumes, can be used to estimate the total CO₂e emissions.

4.3 Exploratory Data Analysis

4.3.1 EDA of Road Traffic Data

In this section, we perform an Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) to investigate road traffic patterns across different vehicle categories. The dataset comprises five distinct vehicle types: Car, Bus, HGV (Heavy Goods Vehicle), Truck, and Motorcycle. Our objective is to analyse the weekly volume patterns of these vehicles and identify key trends in road usage.

From our initial analysis, we observe that cars overwhelmingly dominate the traffic volume, followed by buses and HGVs Fig. 13. This finding underscores the significant role of private vehicles in daily commuting, while public transport and freight movement also contribute substantially to road activity.

Figure 13: Vehicle Volume Distribution on M8 (by week)

To gain deeper insights, we conduct a detailed daily volume analysis for the three vehicle types with the highest traffic volumes: Car, Bus, and HGV. The objective is to understand how their usage varies across different days of the week, identifying potential fluctuations between weekdays and weekends.

As shown in Fig 14, cars dominate road traffic, particularly during commuting hours. Given their lower occupancy rates, private cars contribute significantly to CO₂ emissions per passenger. Encouraging electric vehicle (EV) adoption and carpooling can mitigate their environmental impact.

Figure 14: Car volume pattern(by day)

Fig 15 indicates that bus volume peaks during rush hours. While fewer in number, buses have a higher passenger capacity, leading to lower per capita emissions. Promoting public transport usage and investing in electric bus fleets can further reduce emissions.

HGVs, as seen in Fig 16, exhibit relatively stable daily traffic patterns. However, they are among the highest CO₂ emitters due to high fuel consumption. Strategies such as route optimisation, rail freight integration, and alternative fuels can significantly curb their emissions.

The findings suggest that cars contribute the most to total emissions, but improving public transport efficiency and freight logistics can achieve significant reductions.

Traffic and Emission Impact During Edinburgh Fringe Festival Large-scale events such as the *Edinburgh Fringe Festival* [2] significantly impact road traffic and emissions. As shown in Fig 17, vehicle volume on the M8 highway increases

Figure 15: Bus volume pattern(by day)

substantially, particularly during peak hours. This surge in traffic leads to severe congestion, further exacerbating fuel consumption and emissions.

Fig 18 illustrates the distribution of vehicle types on the M8 during the festival period. Consistent with previous findings, cars dominate the traffic flow, reinforcing their substantial contribution to overall greenhouse gas emissions. While buses and HGVs maintain a relatively stable presence, the overwhelming reliance on private vehicles underscores the environmental burden associated with such events.

The combined effect of increased car usage and prolonged congestion results in higher CO₂e emissions, particularly from idling and stop-and-go traffic conditions. Encouraging alternative transport modes, such as rail or shared mobility solutions, could play a crucial role in mitigating the environmental impact of mass gatherings.

Quantifying Travel-Related Greenhouse Gas Emissions This section estimates the GHG emissions associated with different modes of transport used

Figure 16: HGV volume pattern(by day)

by festival-goers travelling to the Edinburgh Fringe Festival. The approach follows a standard calculation method, using the formula:

$$\text{GHG emissions} = \text{Activity data} \times \text{Emission conversion factor}$$

GHG emissions are measured in carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e), which accounts for the impact of various greenhouse gases converted into CO₂-equivalent values. The activity data considers the distance travelled and the number of passengers, while the emission conversion factor is derived from official figures provided by the UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA)[4].

To assess the environmental impact of travel, this study examines two common transport scenarios: car travel and rail travel over a 75km distance. In the case of car travel, it is assumed that 1,000 people travel by car, with an average occupancy of 2.5 passengers per vehicle. Using DEFRA’s emission factor of 0.169 kg CO₂e per km, the total emissions are calculated as:

Figure 17: Peak Congestion Hours on M8 (During Edinburgh Fringe Fest 2023)

$$\frac{1000}{2.5} \times 75 \times 0.169 = 5,095 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e}$$

For the rail travel scenario, the analysis assumes that five train services each carry 200 passengers over the same 75km journey. Using rail emission factor of DEFRA of 0.035 kg CO₂e per passenger-km, the total emissions for rail travel are:

$$5 \times 200 \times 75 \times 0.035 = 2,659 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e}$$

The detailed CO₂e emission calculation above shows that rail travel produces considerably lower emissions per passenger compared to car travel, highlighting its environmental advantages for large-scale public events. Encouraging greater use of rail transport could be an effective strategy for reducing the overall carbon footprint of festival-related travel. However, this study does not account for other forms of transport, such as buses, the Glasgow Subway, or shared mobility services, all of which could influence travel patterns and emissions. Future research could incorporate these additional transport options and examine potential shifts in travel behaviour to promote sustainable mobility solutions further.

Figure 18: Percentage of Vehicle Type Distribution on M8(During Edinburgh Fringe Fest 2023)

5 Results & Discussions

5.1 ScotRail: Network Disruptions Insights

In this section, we present key insights into the ScotRail network disruptions derived from our analysis. Our approach is twofold: first, we quantify the disruptions using metrics such as average delay times and passenger counts, which provide a broad overview of how the network responds during various events. Second, we drill down into a specific case study—the Ayr Station fire incident—to examine the localised impact in greater detail. By comparing pre- and post-incident data, we not only highlight the immediate effects on rail services and departure counts but also uncover broader behavioural shifts, such as increased road traffic in the surrounding area. This dual analysis helps to paint a comprehensive picture of disruption dynamics within the ScotRail network and underscores the value of combining quantitative metrics with in-depth case studies to inform future transport management and decarbonization strategies.

5.1.1 Key metrics to measure disruptions

In this section, we explore key metrics used to quantify network disruptions across the ScotRail system. Generally, a transportation network under strain is likely to exhibit travel delays. So this metric was the first under study. However, delays around Edinburgh Waverley station during both the Fringe Festival and the weather event (disruptions in red) are comparable to those during normal conditions (blue) - see Figure 19. ScotRail network, hence, shows no strain in the form of travel delays. This is likely because the rail network usually runs under capacity ($\approx < 20\%$ during regular days), and no significant new trains are added to increase travel delays. This is unlike a road network, where a road network is likely to see more cars on the road, resulting in more travel time during journeys.

Figure 19: Characterising disruptions through time delay and passenger counts in Edinburgh station Red colour line plots indicate the period of disruption due to a particular event under study. A. Delay time during Fringe festival, B. Passenger count during fringe festival, C. Delay time during storm, and D. Passenger count during storm

In contrast, normalised passenger counts present a different story. Passenger numbers exhibit significant changes: a pronounced spike during the Fringe Festival, consistent with the influx of millions of visitors, and a sharp decline during the yellow warning period, reflecting reduced travel as people stay indoors. These insights suggest that while delay metrics may not fully capture the impact of disruptions, fluctuations in passenger counts serve as a more sensitive indicator of network disturbance.

5.1.2 Evaluating Disruption Impact - Ayr Station Fire Incident

Figure 20: Impact of Ayr station fire on the passenger count across all rail lines that serve Ayr station. Red dotted line indicates the period of separation for before and after the Ayr station fire incident

Figure 21: Impact of Ayr station fire on the passenger count in adjacent and other stations. Red dotted line indicates the period of separation for before and after the Ayr station fire incident

In this case study, we examined two key metrics—rail services and passenger counts—to evaluate the impact of the fire incident at Ayr Station. Figure 20 illustrates that before the fire, Ayr Station consistently maintained nearly 100% rail service levels, with departure counts following a steady upward trend that reflected stable and growing passenger demand. However, following the fire on September 25, 2023 (indicated by the red dashed vertical line), both rail services and departure counts experienced a sharp decline. Although rail services recovered quickly to pre-disruption levels, the departure counts remained significantly lower, suggesting that the incident may have altered passenger behaviour or station usage patterns, with a reduction in passengers from Ayr station (which was closed for several months), reduced the overall number of passengers who take rail transport.

Figure 22: Visualising road exits in the vicinity of Ayr City

The impact of the disruption was not confined to Ayr Station alone. As shown in Figure 21, neighbouring stations along the same service line exhibited similar patterns of decline and recovery. For instance, Kilmaurs, the furthest station served by multiple train lines, saw its passenger numbers eventually return to pre-fire levels. This indicates that while the disruption had a noticeable local effect, its long-term impact varied regionally.

To further enrich our analysis, we incorporated road traffic data around Ayr City,

Figure 23: Impact of Ayr station fire on the road traffic in the vicinity of Ayr City. Red dotted line: date of Ayr station fire.

focusing solely on vehicle counts for cars to simplify the assessment. The road network was divided into three categories as shown in Figure 22: main city exits (blue), roads leading toward Prestwick Airport (yellow), and outer city exits (green). As visualised in Figure 23, a sharp increase in normalised vehicle counts was observed following the incident, especially along the main exits of Ayr city. Even a modest rise in vehicle counts highlights a significant behavioural shift, likely reflecting that affected passengers chose to travel by car instead of using rail services.

5.1.3 Interactive demo of ScotRail Network

Understanding the evolution of the traffic system and its modelling is essential for informed decision-making. Due to time constraints, the DSG team has not yet fully developed an in-house diffusion model (not only for analysing past traffic patterns but also for predicting future trends, thereby enhancing decision-making processes) for both railway and road traffic. However, we anticipate that this model would be of interest to the challenge owner. If developed in the future, integrating a downstream visualisation of the diffusion model would be a valuable

addition.

Figure 24 is a demo for visualising a dynamic graph network for traffic flow analysis, where both railway nodes and road traffic nodes evolve over time. The goal is to represent the changing state of the transportation network in an animated format, allowing for the analysis of movement patterns, congestion levels, and interactions between different transportation modes.

The interval can be customised by users. In the example shown in Figure 24, passenger counts over a 24-hour (24 frames for the animation) period on 3rd May 2023 are analysed. Each hour, the total number of passengers at each railway station is recorded and aggregated. The key features are:

- Time-based evolution. Each frame represents a specific moment in traffic movement, making it useful for studying patterns over time for the entire ScotRail network.
- Interactive analysis. The animation controls allow users to pause, replay, or move to specific time steps, facilitating in-depth examination of traffic behaviour.

Note that, by leveraging a stack data structure, the dynamic graph network can efficiently perform real-time analysis while ensuring computational efficiency.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

In summary, our study demonstrates that network science offers a robust framework for evaluating transportation disruptions. While we have not completely taken advantage of it, the potential for studying disruption propagation can be better done robustly when the ScotRail network is rightly assumed to be connected as a single system, affected by events near and far.

Notably, we found that changes in passenger counts serve as a more sensitive and effective metric for measuring disruption than traditional delay metrics. The Ayr case study exemplifies this, revealing that a disruption at a single node can propagate significant impacts across entire rail lines. Moreover, our analysis highlights critical implications for decarbonization: disruptions in rail services not only diminish rail efficiency but also lead to increased reliance on road transport, thereby escalating the carbon footprint. These findings underscore the importance of integrating comprehensive, cross-sector data to better predict and

Figure 24: A dynamic graph network that visualises traffic flow over time. Blue dots represent railway stations, with the size of the nodes reflecting the total number of passengers during the specified time period. Red dots represent road traffic nodes where vehicles are tracked.

mitigate the cascading effects of disruptions. Overall, our results provide actionable insights that can inform strategies to enhance rail service resilience and support sustainable, low-carbon transportation systems.

The analysis of ScotRail travel flow between 2023 and 2024 reveals distinct seasonal peaks, with the highest levels of passenger activity occurring in May, mid-August, and December. The December holiday season stands out as the busiest period of the year, likely driven by increased travel demand for festive celebrations, shopping, and holiday commuting.

The most frequently used stations during this period include Glasgow Central, Glasgow Queen Street, Edinburgh Waverley, Paisley Gilmour Street, and Croy, reinforcing their status as major transport hubs within the network. In contrast, in the Aberdeen area, there is a significantly lower reliance on rail services, with a greater dependency on private vehicles, indicating potential gaps in public transport accessibility or preferences for road travel in that region.

One limitation of this research is that it does not account for the use of other transport modes, such as the Glasgow Subway, buses, and shared mobility services, which could influence overall travel patterns. Future research could explore whether these alternative transport options contribute to reducing car usage or affect demand for rail travel, particularly in urban areas with well-developed multimodal networks. Meanwhile, as the busiest rail routes is between Glasgow Queen Street and Edinburgh Waverley, other rail routes may have a weaker influence in encouraging people to choose rail over private vehicles.

Our study has laid the groundwork for understanding the network dynamics of rail disruptions and their broader implications on passenger flows and carbon emissions. Building on these findings, future work will pursue several key directions:

- **Advanced Predictive Modelling:** Integrate network metrics (e.g., station centrality, connectivity) with real-time passenger flow and disruption data using machine learning to enhance prediction accuracy.
- **Multi-Dimensional Disruption Analysis:** analyse disruptions across various temporal (daily to seasonal) and spatial scales (station to network-wide) and develop a framework for categorising disruptions by severity and propagation.
- **Multi-Modal and Environmental Impact Assessment:** Expand the analysis to include other transport modes, refine CO₂ emission models using industry frameworks, and study how behavioural shifts during disruptions affect overall mobility and emissions.
- **Simulation, Scenario Testing & Policy Evaluation:** Build simulation frameworks, such as diffusion models, to test different disruption scenarios, assess network resilience, and evaluate the economic and policy impacts of targeted interventions.
- **Data Enhancement:** Improve data collection efforts, particularly for intermediate stops and real-time incident reporting, to reduce estimation risks and strengthen model reliability.

7 Team members

Clive Drowley: Clive is a PhD researcher at the EPSRC CDT in Geospatial Systems, a collaboration between Newcastle University and the University of Nottingham. He holds a first-class Geography degree from the University of Leeds, where he won the Society for Location Analysis – Undergraduate Dissertation Award and the Joanna Stillwell Prize. He also studied Computer Science in Eindhoven and learned Mandarin in Wuhan through the Generation UK program. Before academia, he worked as a Data Scientist and Data Engineer, specialising in retail location planning, human mobility, and connected vehicle data. He recently completed an MRes in Geospatial Data Science with distinction at Newcastle University, in partnership with Nokia Bell Labs and UCL, earning a Consumer Data Research Centre Dissertation Prize. His PhD focuses on the modifiable unit area problem, spatial scale, and consumer data.

Jian Feng: Jian is a recent graduate from the London School of Economics (LSE) with an MSc in Geographic Data Science, following his data scientist role in Consumer Data Research Centre and undergraduate studies at the University of Leeds. His research focuses on urban spatial analysis, and he is currently working as a Data Research Assistant at The Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA), contributing to projects involving the West Midlands Fire Service and location accessibility analysis for a charity. He has previous experience with UN-HABITAT and has worked as a journalist and policy research intern for a local council. His contributions to this report include ScotRail network node analysis, data visualisation, time series statistical analysis on rail passenger travel flow, and report writing.

Rishika Gupta: Rishika is a recent graduate from CentraleSupélec - Université Paris-Saclay, France, where she earned her Master's degree in Big Data Management and Analytics. Prior to that, she completed her Bachelor's in computer engineering from the University of Mumbai, India. With experience spanning anomaly detection, time series analysis, and working with diverse data domains—including geospatial data—she has built a strong foundation in both research and practical applications. In this project, she contributed significantly to brainstorming sessions, the implementation of the ScotRail network disruption analysis, and the evaluation of event impacts. Additionally, she played a key role in compiling the documentation and delivering presentations, ensuring that complex insights were effectively communicated.

Ajaykumar Manivannan: Ajay is a Research Fellow at the University of Leeds,

Leeds, UK. His research interests include Network Science, Human Mobility, GenAI, ABM, and Computational Social Science. He holds a master's degree in Aerospace Engineering from the Technical University of Munich, Germany, and Nanyang Technological University, Singapore. His contributions to this study include developing the research framework for Approach 1, building and analysing the ScotRail network, and studying the effect of disruptions in the ScotRail network using rail and road traffic data.

Antalya Martinez Plata: Antalya is a recent graduate from the University of Essex with an MSc in Statistics. Prior to that, she completed her BSc in Applied Mathematics at ITAM, Mexico. Antalya is set to begin a role as a Graduate Engineer at Riverlane, where she will contribute to the Quantum Error Correction (QEC) stack to help make quantum computing useful sooner. In this project, she worked on dataset joins, cancellation and addition analysis, and proposed future directions for improving the estimation approach.

Trisha Punamiya: Trisha is a current graduate student at the London School of Economics pursuing a Masters in Public Administration: Data Science for Public Policy program. Prior to this, she worked at Analysis Group, an economic consulting firm, where she contributed on the economic analyses on various Antitrust, Class Action, Intellectual Property lawsuits. She obtained her bachelor's degrees in Economics and Statistical Science from Southern Methodist University.

Hyesop Shin: Hyesop is a Lecturer in GIScience at the School of Environment, University of Auckland. He is also an Affiliated Research Fellow at the School of Health and Wellbeing, University of Glasgow. He has broad interests in environmental hazards, urban air quality, transport in low emission zones, and agent-based modelling (ABM). His contribution to this project was in the areas of emissions calculation, data review, slide preparation, and contextualisation.

Pingfan Wang: Pingfan is a lecturer at the Department of Computer and Information Sciences at Northumbria University. He received his PhD in December 2023, specializing in concept drift detection and time series analysis. His research focuses on explainable AI, time series integration, and large language model applications, particularly in areas such as extreme weather prediction and efficient real-time learning. With a background in computer science and machine learning, he has expertise in data acquisition, modeling, and AI-driven solutions. In addition to research, he teaches courses on Data Science and AI, with a focus on Big Data and Data Analysis.

Xiaoxue Shen: Xiaoxue Shen joined the TRIC-DT team at the Alan Turing Institute in October 2023 as a Postdoctoral Research Associate, focusing on Neuro-Symbolic AI for Digital Twins. Xiaoxue contributed to this project by scoping the challenge approaches, interactive dynamic graph development, etc.

References

- [1] [n. d.]. Scotland's Census: Transport. <https://www.scotlandscensus.gov.uk/census-results/at-a-glance/transport/>
- [2] Xela Batchelder. 2006. *The world's largest arts festival, The Edinburgh Festival Fringe: mechanics, myth and management*. Ph.D. Dissertation. The Ohio State University.
- [3] Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. 2025. 2023 UK Greenhouse Gas Emissions, Final Figures. <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/67a30e4f7da1f1ac64e5feb1/2023-final-greenhouse-gas-emissions-statistical-release.pdf>
Statistical release.
- [4] Office for National Statistics. 2024. Measuring UK Greenhouse Gas Emissions. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/environmentalaccounts/methodologies/measuringukgreenhousegasemissions> Last revised 17 October 2024.
- [5] Carlos Mougán, Richard Plant, Clare Teng, Marya Bazzi, Alvaro Cabrejas Egea, Ryan Sze-Yin Chan, David Salvador Jasin, Martin Stoffel, Kirstie J. Whitaker, and Jules Manser. 2023. How to Data in Datathons. In *NeurIPS*.

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

turing.ac.uk
@turinginst